

The Role of Attribution Theory and Symbolic Status on Consumers' Luxury Brand Attitudes: A Comparison Between Consumers in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia*

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Article Info

Research article

Received: 06.10.2025

Accepted: 07.01.2026

Published: 19.04.2026

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Keywords:

Luxury Brand
Attribution Theory
Symbolic Status
Conspicuous Consumption

Jel Codes:

M31
D12
D91

Abstract

Prestigious brands significantly shape consumer preferences by leveraging symbolic and emotional resonance. Consumers often perceive the consumption of these brands as a means of satisfying hedonic needs. While Attribution Theory posits that individuals utilize specific characteristics and cognitive schemas to evaluate brands, this study investigates how such attitudes are constructed within the contexts of symbolic status and attribution in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia. Focusing on the psychological and social determinants of luxury consumption, the research specifically examines the fashion industry. The survey targeted individuals who prioritize brand status or personal self-congruity. Based on an analysis of 293 respondents (144 from Saudi Arabia, 125 from Türkiye, and 24 from other regions), the findings indicate that brand prestige exerts a direct positive influence on symbolic status. Notably, Attribution Theory was found to have no mediating effect within this specific dynamic. The original value of this study lies in its pioneering nature, as it represents the first comparative research conducted between Türkiye and Saudi Arabia in this specific field. Furthermore, it contributes to the existing literature by uniquely utilizing Attribution Theory as a mediating variable in relation to brands within the fashion industry. The results suggest that the correlation between prestige and symbolic status manifests in social interactions, professional environments, and general consumer behavior. Luxury brands remain preferred because they provide the prestige and status necessary for self-expression and upward social mobility. Furthermore, the study highlights a distinction in consumer evaluation: brand associations are prioritized for utilitarian products, whereas emotional and aesthetic values remain paramount for hedonic goods. Future research should encompass diverse cultural and socio-economic demographics to enhance the generalizability of these findings.

Tüketicilerin Lüks Marka Tutumlarında Atıf Teorisi ve Sembolik Statünün Rolü:

Türkiye ve Suudi Arabistan'daki Tüketiciler Arasında Bir Karşılaştırma

Makale Bilgisi

Araştırma Makalesi

Başvuru: 06.10.2025

Kabul: 07.01.2026

Yayın: 19.04.2026

*Sorumlu Yazar: Adnan KARA

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Lüks Marka
Atıf Teorisi
Sembolik Statü
Gösterişli Tüketim

Jel Kodları:

Özet

Prestijli markalar, sembolik ve duygusal bir rezonans oluşturarak tüketici tercihlerini önemli ölçüde şekillendirmektedir. Tüketiciler, bu markaların tüketimini genellikle hedonik (hazcı) ihtiyaçları tatmin etmenin bir aracı olarak algılamaktadır. Atfetme Teorisi, bireylerin markaları değerlendirmek için belirli özellikleri ve bilişsel şemaları kullandığını ileri sürerken; bu çalışma, söz konusu tutumların Türkiye ve Suudi Arabistan bağlamında sembolik statü ve atıf çerçevesinde nasıl inşa edildiğini incelemektedir. Lüks tüketiminin psikolojik ve sosyal belirleyicilerine odaklanan araştırma, özellikle moda endüstrisini ele almaktadır. Anket çalışması, marka statüsüne veya kişisel benlik uyumuna (self-congruity) öncelik veren bireyleri hedeflemiştir. 293 katılımcıdan (144 Suudi Arabistan, 125 Türkiye ve 24 diğer bölgeler) elde edilen verilerin analizine dayanarak; bulgular, marka prestijinin sembolik statü üzerinde doğrudan pozitif bir etkisi olduğunu göstermektedir. Dikkat çekici bir şekilde, atfetme teorisi'nin bu dinamik içerisinde aracı (mediator) bir etkisinin olmadığı tespit edilmiştir. Bu çalışmanın özgün değeri, ilgili alanda Türkiye ve Suudi Arabistan arasında

M31
D12
D91

yürütülen ilk karşılaştırmalı araştırma olmasından kaynaklanan öncü niteliğinde yatmaktadır. Ayrıca çalışma, Atfetme Teorisi'ni moda endüstrisindeki markalarla ilişkili olarak özgün bir şekilde aracı değişken olarak kullanarak mevcut literatüre katkı sağlamaktadır. Sonuçlar, prestij ve sembolik statü arasındaki korelasyonun sosyal etkileşimlerde, profesyonel yaşamda ve genel tüketici davranışlarında kendini gösterdiğini savunmaktadır. Lüks markalar, tüketicilere kendilerini ifade etme ve sosyal hiyerarşide daha üst bir konuma ulaşma noktasında gerekli prestij ve statüyü sağladığı için tercih edilmeye devam etmektedir. Dahası çalışma, tüketici değerlendirmesinde bir ayrıma dikkat çekmektedir: Faydacı (utilitarian) ürünlerde marka çağrışımlarına öncelik verilirken, hedonik ürünlerde duygusal ve estetik değerler temel belirleyici olmaktadır. Gelecekteki araştırmalar, bulguların genellenebilirliğini artırmak için farklı kültürel ve sosyo-ekonomik demografik grupları kapsamalıdır.

*This paper is derived from the thesis.

To cite this article: Kara, A. & Hamoudy, G. (2026). The Role of Attribution Theory and Symbolic Status on Consumers' Luxury Brand Attitudes: A Comparison Between Consumers in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia, *Siyaset, Ekonomi ve İşletme Bilimleri Dergisi*, Cilt:6 (Sayı:1), s.99-117.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19646395>

Introduction

Throughout history, every seller has tended to use a symbol to differentiate their products from others. Although the concept of a brand has changed over time in terms of form, name, and function, it has continued to exist. A brand, considered a distinctive symbol of a product or service, is one of the factors forming the foundation of successful companies and modern societies. No matter what is offered, any product or service has established physical and psychological connections with certain brands in specific categories. This indicates that the brand goes beyond being just a logo, becoming a distinct identity associated with a particular product or service and an exclusive experience for customers.

Branding plays a critical role in the success of institutions and companies in today's world. A brand conveys the message, value, and competitive advantage of the product or service offered to customers and consumers (El Alak, 1996). Additionally, a brand establishes long-term relationships between consumers and products based on trust, loyalty, and satisfaction (El Alak, 1996). Among the different types of branding, luxury brands stand out, especially as a model of success and excellence in the business and consumer world.

This study is important for understanding the position of luxury brands in the minds of consumers and identifying the factors that shape the perception of these brands. A deep analysis of consumer behavior toward luxury brands in different cultural contexts, such as Türkiye and Saudi Arabia, will contribute to more effectively guiding marketing strategies.

This research emphasizes how the emotional and symbolic connections between consumers and brands affect purchasing decisions using attribution theory and symbolic status. It can also contribute to the determination of marketing strategies. Identifying strategies that will

strengthen consumers' expectations and their relationship with the brand is critical for the successful marketing of luxury brands.

The primary aim of this study is to deeply examine consumer attitudes toward luxury brands and investigate the impact of symbolism and attribution theories on consumer behavior across different cultural contexts in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia. The objectives of this study include comparing consumer attitudes toward symbolic and attributed values of brands, identifying cultural differences.

1. Theoretical Background

1.1. Luxury Brand

The word luxury is derived from the Latin word "Luxus," which means to stimulate the senses, regardless of the cost. Luxury brands are known for their high prices despite offering a low tangible benefit ratio and are generally brands that provide high intangible benefits (Nueno & Quelch, 1998). Luxury is a relative term that can mean almost anything or nothing at all, depending on whom you ask (Nueno & Quelch, 1998). For instance, a Lexus may be considered a luxury car for an ordinary student, while for a wealthy individual, it may be seen as an ordinary car.

Formulating the definition of a luxury brand is difficult because luxury is a complex concept that varies from person to person. Although everyone can decide which brands deserve the "luxury" label and which do not, it is challenging to formulate a precise definition of this concept (Kapferer, 1998). It can generally be said that consumption products that attract the interest of the upper-income group, have a high price, and are of advanced quality are considered luxury products (Tıǧlı & Akyazgan, 2003).

Luxury brands represent more than just products for consumers. When choosing a luxury brand, consumers consider not only the quality or functionality of the product but also psychological factors such as social status, the pursuit of exclusivity, and identity (Nueno & Quelch, 1998). However, the concept of luxury is subjective and lacks a clear definition, varying from person to person.

Consumers of luxury brands are often driven by the desire to elevate their social status, prove their belonging to a certain class, or seek exclusivity. Brand preferences can vary based on factors such as gender, lifestyle, and personal values (Stokburger-Sauer & Teichmann, 2013). For instance, women tend to have a more positive attitude toward luxury brands, while men are generally more focused on product performance and price (Stokburger-Sauer &

Teichmann, 2013). However, many consumers form emotional bonds with brands and see them as an integral part of their personality.

Therefore, it is important to consider many different factors to understand and analyze the behaviours of luxury brand consumers. Brand managers can combine these factors to gain a deeper understanding of consumers' needs and adjust their marketing strategies accordingly. Consumer research has proven that luxury is associated with features that are perceived as truly exceptional, surpassing functional values, and are characterized by rarity, quality, natural materials, or craftsmanship. However, there is no clear, indisputable definition (Vanhamme, Lindgreen, & Sarial-Abi, 2023). It can be said that a luxury brand consists of everything that signifies elegance, luxury, and distinction with uniqueness, high quality, unique designs, and comfort.

1.2. Prestige Brand Consumption

Most luxury brand consumers seek to improve their social status in the eyes of those around them, prove that they belong to a particular class, or pursue uniqueness or distinction when purchasing luxury products. The consumer's desire for luxury is largely driven by the need for status (respect, admiration, etc.) provided by others (Dubois, Jung, & Ordabayeva, 2021).

Research highlighting lifestyle differences that affect consumption preferences emphasizes gender differences in brand preferences. Men often focus more on utility, performance, functionality, and price rather than appearance, while women tend to prioritize society, form, and design over performance. Women generally have a more positive attitude toward luxury brands compared to men. The more a consumer identifies with a brand, the stronger their brand loyalty becomes (Stokburger-Sauer & Teichmann, 2013).

There are numerous typologies used in consumer classification. Consumers who purchase a brand's product may do so because they consider the benefits it offers, because they admire the brand, or for other reasons. Some consumers buy a brand's product simply because they have the opportunity to do so, even if they don't know what the brand is. There are also consumers who prefer a brand because they feel a sense of belonging to it. These consumers cannot switch brands because they feel that being associated with the brand is a part of their identity. Therefore, the perceptions of brand consumers vary. However, despite their different preferences, there are similarities between women and men in terms of consuming the brand (Stokburger-Sauer & Teichmann, 2013).

Luxury brand consumers are driven by deep motivations that include not only the quality or functionality of products but also psychological factors related to social status, the pursuit of privilege, and identity (Nueno & Quelch, 1998). The concept of luxury can mean different things to different people and lacks a clear definition. However, luxury items are generally considered to be expensive, high-quality products that appeal to higher income groups. Consumers' brand preferences can vary based on many factors, including gender, lifestyle, and personal values (Nueno & Quelch, 1998). To understand and analyze this complexity, brand managers need to consider a wide range of factors and shape their marketing strategies by better understanding consumers' needs. In short, understanding the behavior of luxury brand consumers is crucial for brand and market strategies.

1.3. Attribution Theory

Attribution theory focuses on uncovering the origins of individuals' or others' actions. People first identify reasons behind behaviors, then act based on these reasons, and finally establish general principles and rules that will guide the entire process. In other words, attribution theory is concerned with understanding origins of human behavior and acting according to these origins. This theory attempts to explain how people interpret actions in a specific context and how these interpretations ultimately lead to their behavior (Şenel, 2019).

Attribution theory explains how people interpret the behaviors and events of others. When determining the cause of behavior, people often point to either internal causes (personal characteristics) or external causes (environmental factors) (Bağcı, 2021). Many factors influence this attribution process, such as consistency, distinctiveness, and behavioral similarity. Different attribution theories offer various explanations for people's behaviors. Marketing attribution theory, which includes factors affecting consumers' purchasing preferences, suggests that positive or negative perceptions of a product or brand have the potential to determine purchasing decisions. Marketing communication can influence the attribution process and shape a company's image through the messages sent to consumers. Factors such as service quality and brand personality are also important in the attribution process (Bağcı, 2021).

People often attribute behavior to internal and external factors, and these judgments influence their actions. From a marketing perspective, attribution can impact consumers' purchasing decisions and shape corporate image (Bağcı, 2021). Specifically, factors such as service quality and brand personality can influence consumers' impressions.

1.4. Symbolic Status

The concept of symbolic status plays a significant role in representing social relationships and individuals' statuses within society, and it has a profound impact on today's consumer culture. The expression of symbolic statuses by individuals and groups through consumption products and brands reflects a certain value or meaning in society (Millan & Reynolds, 2014). Symbolic status can manifest in various ways, depending on internal and external motivations, and it plays an important role in consumers' processes of expressing their identities and determining their place in society (Buluk & Erdem, 2019).

Symbolic Status refers to symbols that represent and convey an individual's or group's status or position in society (Millan & Reynolds, 2014). These symbols are often expressed through consumer products or brands and carry specific meanings or values in society. For example, a luxury car or clothing brand can play a symbolic role in conveying its owner's high social status. Symbolic status is an important tool used by people to express their identity, communicate their self-image, and define their place in society (Millan & Reynolds, 2014).

Symbolic status is the process through which consumers communicate and form their identities through products (Chiesa & Dekker, 2024). Consumption extends beyond mere functionality and has a symbolic dimension; it supports consumers in expressing their identities. Symbolic meanings vary according to cultural and social contexts and are attributed to products by consumers. Major brands or widely recognized products may not always be suitable for consumers to express their uniqueness; thus, small-scale production, local brands, and companies outside the mainstream can enhance their symbolic status. The process of evaluating and interpreting symbolic meanings emphasizes the active role of consumers (Chiesa & Dekker, 2024).

Symbolic Status is a concept that expresses individuals' status and image in society, providing them with status and visibility from others. This status is demonstrated through the goods or services a person possesses and is often associated with luxury products and prestige. Symbolic status can be expressed in different ways depending on an individual's internal or external motivations. Internal motivations might lead a person to focus on self-fulfillment or satisfaction, while external motivations may focus more on increasing visible status within society. Therefore, symbolic status is an element that affects people's consumption behaviours and represents their identity and position in society (Buluk & Erdem, 2019). The concept is frequently studied in social sciences and marketing, and is often used to examine its effects on consumer behaviour, lifestyle, and reputation (Loureiro, Japutra, & Kwun, 2019).

2. Research Method

2.1. Aim of Study

This research aims to thoroughly investigate consumer attitudes toward luxury brands and to explore the impact of symbolic status and attribution theories on consumer behaviours in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia across different cultural contexts. The focus of the study is on the lack of sufficient research examining psychological, cultural, and social factors influencing attitudes toward luxury brands through symbolic status and attribution theories. Additionally, this issue is important for determining how psychological, social, and cultural factors that shape consumer behavior towards luxury brands affect consumers' identities, self-perceptions, and values through their preferences.

The results of this research can guide luxury brand managers and marketing professionals in better understanding their target audiences and shaping their marketing strategies accordingly. Additionally, understanding the differences in consumer attitudes in different cultural contexts can have a significant impact on the development of international marketing strategies. In this way, the research is expected to contribute to the theoretical and practical understanding of the luxury brand sector, leading to the creation of more effective marketing strategies and enhancing the competitive edge of luxury brands.

2.2. Research Design

The research includes consumer surveys targeting luxury brands operating in the "Fashion" sector. The survey targets all individuals who value the status or personal suitability of brands, regardless of their income level, and therefore show interest in these brands. The sample for the research includes internet users who are 18 years old or older, and citizens or residents of Türkiye and Saudi Arabia. Data was collected through an online survey tool.

In the survey, participants were presented with brands. The brands used in the survey were: "LOUIS VUITTON, BURBERRY, PRADA, ROLEX, HERMES, CHANEL, GUCCI, RALPH LAUREN".

Participants were given scenarios to imagine before responding. In the first scenario, the following question was asked: (Imagine you are attending a social event and you meet someone for the first time. When they come to greet you, you notice that they are wearing clothing and accessories from one of the following luxury brands: (LOUIS VUITTON, BURBERRY, PRADA, ROLEX, HERMÈS, CHANEL, GUCCI, RALPH LAUREN).

The survey includes questions related to consumer demographics. Scales related to "Attribution Theory and Symbolic Status" have been used to measure consumer attitudes. The

survey has been prepared in both Turkish and Arabic. The questions have been translated from English and verified for accuracy by experts.

The survey data has been analyzed using SPSS and the results have been interpreted accurately and objectively. The research was conducted from start to finish with the approval of the Bayburt University Ethics Comitee 27.02.2024-190379 date and number decision and in accordance with ethical standards that confirm the seriousness of the research process and respect for rights and ethics. The scales used in the survey were adapted from: symbolic status (Şahin, 2018); attribution (Şahin, 2018); prestige, (Ho et al. 2023). The reliability of the scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (Prestige, 0.881; Symbolic status, 0.857; Attribution, 0.789).

2.3. Research Model

The study focuses on a research model developed to understand the significant psychological and social dynamics that shape and motivate luxury consumption preferences. The research model considers three main factors to understand consumers' luxury consumption behaviours: prestige, symbolic status, and brand attribution. The framework is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source(s): Authors own creation

The study's Hypotheses are:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Prestige (X) will have a positive and significant direct effect on Symbolic Status (Y).

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Prestige (X) will have a positive and significant effect on Attribution (M).

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Attribution (M) will have a positive and significant effect on Symbolic Status (Y), even after controlling for Prestige (X).

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Attribution (M) will mediate the relationship between Prestige (X) and Symbolic Status (Y).

2.4. Research Materials

Data were collected through an online survey in Türkiye and Saudi Arabia. The sample frame consists of mobile phone users who are familiar with at least one of the following brands: “Louis Vuitton, Burberry, Prada, Rolex, Hermes, Chanel, Gucci, Ralph Lauren.” The sample frame includes citizens, residents of the region, and individuals aged 18 and over, both high and low income. The survey was written in Arabic for Saudi citizens and foreigners residing in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and in Turkish for Turkish citizens and foreigners residing in Türkiye. The questions were translated from English and reviewed by experts to ensure their accuracy.

The survey was sent to a total of 500 people from different regions of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia using email and social media platforms. A convenience sampling method was employed. Due to budget and time constraints, the survey was sent to close contacts (family, friends, social media followers, communities, students, and professors) and they were asked to complete the survey and share it with their friends and colleagues. A total of 293 people participated, resulting in a response rate of 58.6%. Among these, 20 participants could not complete the survey or failed the “control question” (Do you know any of the following brands: “Louis Vuitton, Burberry, Prada, Rolex, Hermes, Chanel, Gucci, Ralph Lauren”?). The valid sample size is 251.

3. Analysis of the Findings

This section focuses on the analysis of survey data aimed at solving the research problem. The survey was conducted to examine consumers’ attitudes toward luxury brands operating in the fashion sector. Additionally, this section includes explanations and interpretations based on the research findings. Various techniques were used to analyze the data in the research. These techniques are: frequency analysis, descriptive analysis, factor analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis. The SPSS 24 program was used to perform these analyses.

3.1. Distribution of Participants According to Demographic Characteristics

Table 1: Demographic Findings of Participants in the “Fashion” First Study

Variables	Sample		Variables	Sample	
	<i>n</i>	%		<i>N</i>	%
Gender			Where do you live		
Male	194	66.2%	Saudi Arabia	144	49.1%
Female	99	33.8%	Türkiye	125	42.7%

Total	293	100.0%	Mauritania	20	6.8%
Age			Iraq	1	0.3%
18 - 24	113	38.6%	Egypt	1	0.3%
25 - 29	91	31.1%	Niger	1	0.3%
30 - 34	37	12.6%	Kuwait	1	0.3%
35 - 39	27	9.2%	Total	293	100.0%
40 - 49	14	4.8%	Origin Country		
50 - 59	10	3.4%	Saudi Arabia	85	29.0%
60 - More	1	0.3%	Türkiye	58	19.8%
Total	293	100.0%	Mauritania	69	23.5%
Civil Status			Syria	29	9.9%
Single	216	73.7%	Palestine	4	1.4%
Married	74	25.3%	Yemen	9	3.1%
Engaged	3	1.0%	Iraq	2	0.7%
Total	293	100.0%	Egypt	11	3.8%
Job Status			Morocco	9	3.1%
Student	131	44.7%	Azerbaijan	1	0.3%
Unemployed	31	10.6%	Turkmenistan	3	1.0%
Retired	2	0.7%	Central Africa Republic	1	0.3%
Freelance	19	6.5%	Iranian	2	0.7%
Temporary Job	4	1.4%	Uzbekistan	1	0.3%
Business Owner	8	2.7%	Burundi	1	0.3%
Government Sector	43	14.7%	Niger	1	0.3%
Private Sector	55	18.8%	Chad	1	0.3%
Total	293	100.0%	Pakistan	1	0.3%
Education			Myanmar	1	0.3%
Primary school	3	1.0%	Sudan	1	0.3%
Middle school	7	2.4%	Afghanistan	1	0.3%
High school	70	23.9%	Lebanon	1	0.3%
Associate Degree	37	12.6%	Algeria	1	0.3%
Bachelor's Degree	128	43.7%	Total	293	100.0%
Master's degree	37	12.6%	Income		
Doctorate Degree	11	3.8%	Lower - 799\$	154	52.6%
Total	293	100.0%	800\$ - 1332\$	72	24.6%
			1333\$ - 2132\$	33	11.3%
			2133\$ - 2665\$	15	5.1%
			2666\$ - More	19	6.5%
			Total	293	100.0%

Table 1 presents key results regarding the demographic characteristics of the participants. Firstly, when examining the gender distribution, it is observed that 66.2% of the participants are male and 33.8% are female. Regarding age distribution, it is noted that the majority are in the 25-34 age range. In terms of marital status, 73.7% of the participants are single. Looking at employment status, it is seen that participants are engaged in various job sectors; 44.7% are students, and 18.8% are employed in the private sector. When examined by educational level, it is observed that the majority of the participants have undergraduate degrees

(43.7%), associate degrees (12.6%), and master's degrees (12.6%). The distribution by place of residence shows a concentration in countries like Saudi Arabia (49.1%) and Türkiye (42.7%). According to country distribution, most participants are from Saudi Arabia, Türkiye, and Mauritania. Regarding income levels, it is determined that 52.6% of the participants are in the lower income bracket, and 6.5% are in the higher income bracket.

3.2. Factor Analysis

Table 3: Results Obtained from the Explanatory Factor Analysis of the Study

Items	Variance Explained	Factor load		
		1	2	3
Factor 1: Symbolic Status	22.629			
My friend is Elite.		.819		
My friend belongs to the Upper class.		.808		
My friend is Prestigious.		.775		
My friend is famous.		.749		
My friend has High status.		.710		
Factor 2: Prestige	3.370			
The products of these brands provide my friend with social acceptance in the environments he/she enters.			.755	
Products from these brands reflect my friend as the person he/she wants to be.			.743	
My friend who uses products of these brands is proud of himself.			.702	
My friends who use products from these brands are visible to me in social environments, and I notice them.			.701	
Products from these brands help my friend express his/her style.			.678	
I have a good impression about my friend who uses products from these brands.			.621	
When I see my friend using products from these brands in social environments, I get an idea about his/her lifestyle.			.527	
Factor 3: Attribution	2.549			
When I think of luxury brands, this is one of them.				.804
These brands are a great example of my image of what luxury goods are.				.770
If I had to name one brand that would represent all luxury products, it would be one of these.				.752

*KMO: 0,836, Chi-square: 2014,826, df: 105, sig.: <.001

The factor analysis results indicate that three different factors have been identified. Symbolic Status Factor: This factor explains a total of 22.629 units of variance. The question

with the highest factor loading is “My friend is elite” (81.9%), while the question with the lowest factor loading is “My friend has high status” (71.0%).

Prestige Factor: This factor explains a total of 3.370 units of variance. The question with the highest factor loading is “The products of these brands provide social acceptance in the environments my friend enters” (75.5%), while the question with the lowest factor loading is “When I see that my friend uses these brands’ products in social settings, I get an idea about his lifestyle” (52.7%).

Attribution Factor: This factor explains a variance of 2.549 units in total. The question with the highest factor loading is “The brand that comes to mind when I think of luxury brands is one of these” (80.4%), while the question with the lowest factor loading is “If I had to name a single brand to represent all luxury products, it would be one of these” (75.2%).

3.3. Correlation Analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis Between Variables of the Study

Variables	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3
1. Prestige	293	4,2170	1,42306	—		
2. Symbolic	293	4,0696	1,57786	,357**	—	
3. Attribution	293	4,5518	1,81363	,412**	,222**	—

According to Table 2, there is a high and positive relationship between Prestige and Attribution (0.412). This indicates that the relationship between the two variables is strong, and as the value of one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well.

Additionally, it shows a weak but significant relationship between Attribution and Symbolic (0.222). This indicates that the relationship between the two variables is weaker, and while there is a tendency for one variable to increase as the other increases, the relationship is less pronounced.

There is a high and significant relationship between Symbolism and Prestige (0.357). This indicates a strong and significant relationship between the two variables.

3.4. Regression Analysis

Table 3: Results Obtained from the Regression Analysis of the Study

Variables	M (Attribution)				Y (Symbolic Status)			
	B	SE	p	β	B	SE	p	β
X (Prestige)	0,525	0,068	0,000	0,412	0,354	0,067	0,000	0,319

M (Attribution)		0,079 0,052 0,133 0,090
	R²=0,170	R²=0,134
	F(1,291)=59,605 p=0,000	F(2,290)=22,417 p=0,000

The regression analysis results in Table 3 show that Brand Prestige has a strong and significant effect on Attribution ($B=0.525$), ($p<0.001$), indicating that higher brand prestige increases the level of attribution. The Standard Error ($SE=0.068$) is low, suggesting that the prediction is reliable. Beta ($\beta=0.412$) illustrates the magnitude and significance of the effect of brand prestige on attribution.

The impact of brand prestige on symbolic status is also strong and significant ($B=0.354$), ($p<0.001$), indicating that higher brand prestige also increases symbolic status. The standard error ($SE=0.067$) is low, which indicates that this estimate is reliable. The beta ($\beta=0.319$) shows the magnitude and importance of the effect of brand prestige on symbolic status.

Figure 2: Regression Analysis Results

In Figure 2, the direct effect between Prestige and Symbolic is shown; it is indicated as ($P=0.000$).

The relationship does not have a direct effect on symbolic status ($B=0.079$, $p=0.133$), meaning that changes in the level of attribution do not significantly affect symbolic status. The standard error ($SE=0.052$) and Beta ($\beta=0.090$) indicate that the effect of the attribution variable on symbolic status is weak.

Figure 3: Regression Analysis Results

4. Results

In the study, various data regarding the demographic characteristics of the participants were obtained. When examining their marital status, it was found that 73.7% of the participants are single. This ratio suggests that a significant portion of the study population does not have responsibilities such as marriage and may therefore have a more flexible lifestyle. Data on the participants' employment status shows that 18.8% work in the private sector. This indicates that the largest percentage of participants have their own income and thus have the ability to consume various brands. Data on education levels shows that most participants have a bachelor's degree. This indicates that the participants are generally university graduates and thus possess a certain level of knowledge and skills.

The data obtained regarding the economic conditions indicate that the majority of the participants are in the lower income bracket. This suggests that the target audience of the study includes a group with economic diversity, reflecting the participants' living standards and preferences. While some participants fall into the lower income bracket, others may have higher income levels. This diversity significantly influences the participants' living conditions, spending habits, and consumption preferences (Adilova, 2015). Economic diversity determines the resources available to individuals in their daily lives, the opportunities they have, and the challenges they face. For example, participants with higher income levels may have access to luxury brands and services, while those in lower income levels might focus on meeting basic needs. This situation allows for a broader evaluation of the study's findings and provides insight into the consumption behaviours of different economic segments.

Symbolic status is a concept that reflects individuals' social positions and identities. This status is shaped by the material and immaterial values that individuals possess. Prestige, on the other hand, is the perception of a person or an object as having high value within society. Prestige is closely related to the desire for recognition and respect from the social environment. In this context, the relationship between prestige and symbolic status is evident in individuals' social relationships, professional life, and consumer behavior.

When viewed from the perspective of consumer behavior, it is evident that prestigious brands and products play a decisive role in consumer preferences. Consumers may prefer prestigious brands to elevate their social status and gain respect in society. This situation also directly affects the marketing strategies of brands. Brands aiming to create a prestigious image

seek to offer luxurious and high-quality products to their target audience, aiming to enhance the symbolic status of these consumers.

The effect of symbolic status on prestige can also be observed in professional life. Graduating from a prestigious university, working for a reputable company, or holding a prominent position raises an individual's status in the workplace. This situation plays a crucial role in career development and success in professional life. Additionally, it is evident that prestige shapes symbolic status in social relationships as well. Being in a respected position in society meets the need for acceptance and respect from one's social circle.

The fourth hypothesis suggests that Attribution Theory plays a mediating role in the relationship between Prestige and Symbolic Status. However, the results of the regression analysis did not support this hypothesis. The analyses show that Brand Attribution does not have a direct effect on Symbolic Status. Changes in the level of attribution do not significantly affect symbolic status.

Attribution Theory attempts to explain how individuals use specific characteristics to evaluate particular brands or products. The theory suggests that consumers consider these associations when evaluating brands or products, and that certain cognitive schemas come into play during this process. However, Hypothesis H4, which examines the impact of this relationship on symbolic status, did not validate the assumption that this theory mediates the connection between prestige and symbolic status.

5. Discussion

The results of the research are consistent with studies on the perceived prestige and symbolic status of luxury brands. For example, in the study conducted by Tor Kadioğlu & Yağcı (2021), it was noted that consumers seeking status have a high sensitivity to prestige, and this sensitivity plays a significant role in the formation of symbolic status. Their study provides an in-depth examination of the impact of prestige on symbolic status, revealing the decisive role of prestige perception in consumer behaviour.

Supporting the existing literature, the findings of this study similarly indicate that the positive relationship between Prestige and Symbolic Status is observable across individuals' social relationships, professional life, and consumer behaviour. This relationship explains why consumers prefer prestigious brands to enhance their social status and how they are perceived within their social circles. Particularly, luxury brands are favored because they provide

consumers with prestige and status, fulfilling their desires to express themselves and achieve a higher position in the social hierarchy.

An important finding highlighted in this study is that prestigious brands influence consumer preferences and marketing strategies. High-prestige brands are preferred by consumers not only because of product quality or functionality but also due to their ability to provide social status and prestige. This situation demonstrates how brands should emphasize prestige elements when developing their marketing strategies. Brands that highlight prestige in their marketing strategies can be more effective by addressing consumers' quest for status.

Findings that indicate attribution theory does not mediate the relationship between prestige and symbolic status are consistent with the study by Ryu et al. (2006). Their study demonstrated that attribution theory is effective in the processing of utilitarian products but does not apply to hedonic products in the same way. This study shows that consumers place more importance on brand associations when evaluating utilitarian products, whereas they focus more on emotional and aesthetic values in the case of hedonic products.

6. Suggestions

Firstly, understanding the impact of brand prestige and symbolic status on consumers is crucial for luxury brands. Research shows that strengthening brand image creates more positive perceptions among consumers and enhances brand loyalty. Therefore, it is important for luxury brands to make efforts to further develop their brand image. One way to achieve this is by improving product quality or offering unique experiences to enhance brand image. Additionally, the strategies used in brand communication also have a significant impact on brand prestige. With the right communication strategies, a brand can create a prestigious and desirable image.

Brand attribution strategies can also help establish a positive relationship between brand prestige and consumers. This strategy can be an effective tool for luxury brands to enhance their prestige. For example, through strategic partnerships and sponsorships, a brand can position itself in a prestigious and desirable place. Particularly, the chosen partnerships and sponsorships should reflect the brand's values and identity. This way, the brand can create a deeper connection with the consumer and increase its prestige.

Future research should include diverse cultural and socio-economic groups to enhance the generalizability of results. This can help brands develop more inclusive and effective marketing strategies. In conclusion, understanding both internal and external motivations of

luxury brands, considering emotional factors, and developing strategies for different markets are crucial for increasing brand loyalty and gaining a competitive advantage.

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